

Adsorptive removal of Methylene blue by citric acid modified *Lantana camara* biomass

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Abstract : In the present study *Lantana camara* biomass (LB) modified with citric acid was effectively utilized as an adsorbent for the removal of Methylene blue (MB) from simulated solution at laboratory scale. LB was characterized with Fourier Transformation Infrared (FT-IR), Scanning Electron Microscopy and point zero charge (pH_{zpc}). The effect of various important parameters viz. pH, initial dye concentration, contact time, and temperature on the removal process of the dye was investigated. The effective adsorption was found to be at pH 8. Further the kinetics of adsorption of MB on adsorbent was investigated by using pseudo-first and pseudo-second order kinetics model. The process of removal was found to be governed by pseudo-second order model. Intraparticle diffusion model was also analyzed for this system. Removal was found to be increased by increasing temperature from 303 to 323 K which indicates the endothermic nature of process. Various two parameter isotherm models viz. Langmuir, Freundlich and Harkin-Jura isotherm were applied on resultant data for equilibrium modeling. Thermodynamic parameters were also calculated for the removal process. It was observed that modified LB was highly efficient for discoloration process.

Keywords : *Lantana* biomass, kinetics, equilibrium isotherm, thermodynamics.

Introduction

Dyes are non-degradable pollutant that released during various industrial processes. More than 10,000 of different commercial dyes and pigments exist and more than 7×10^5 tons are manufactured worldwide annually¹. Effluent bearing dyes from a wide variety of sources, such as textiles, printing, dyeing etc. aggravate serious environmental impacts such as raises chemical oxygen demand, dissolved and suspended solids, impede penetration of sunlight, interfere with photosynthetic activity of aquatic plants, and hinder growth of microbes as well as aquatic florafauna. There is considerable need to treat these effluents prior to their discharge into receiving streams. From earlier decades various techniques being employed for removal of colors from dye contaminated water that include adsorption, biodegradation, chemical oxidation, coagulation, electrochemical, Fenton's reagent, membrane filtration, ozonation, ultrasounds etc. Out of these processes of treatment, adsorption process considered to be most effective due to its cost effectiveness, great efficiency and simple operational practice. Activated

carbon is one of the most popular adsorbent, but its high prices as well as high operating costs and problem regeneration leads to impede its large scale application. Therefore, there is a rising need in finding cost effective, renewable, locally available materials as sorbent for the removal of dye colors. Lignocellulosic enriched agricultural based adsorbents have been gaining wide attentions these years, owing to their characteristics, including renewable, biodegradable, environmentally friendly, low cost and abundant in availability.

Some of the biological materials that have been used as adsorbent for dye adsorption from wastewater included mango seed powder², jute processing waste³, rice hull⁴, wheat shell⁵, marine green alga⁶, yellow passion fruit waste⁷, guava leaf powder⁸, cotton wastes⁹, meranti saw dust¹⁰, carrot stem and leaf powder¹¹, milled sugarcane¹² and strychnos potatorum seeds¹³. The present study investigated the use of a previously untried biosorbent, biomass of exotic weed *Lantana camara* for the removal of basic dye methylene blue from its aqueous solution. The modification of adsorbent further carried out with citric

acid that greatly enhanced the sorption capacity of these biomaterials by introducing free carboxyl group of citric acid that results in increase of net negative charge on the adsorbent¹⁴. Thus the method used in the present study for modification purpose is non toxic and energy efficient. Methylene blue (Fig. 1), a thiazine dye, used in the textile, printing, and paint industries. It is very dangerous dye causes severe skin irritation, gastrointestinal tract infection, chest pain, labored breathing and carcinogenic also. As an adsorbent the Lantana biomass is a complex material consisted of several metabolites such as mono and sesquiterpenes, triterpenes, tridoidglycosides, furanonaphthoquinones, flavonoids, phenyl ethanoid glycosides, steroids etc.¹⁵. These metabolites help in binding of dye molecules by donating a pair of electron to form complexes. Further the kinetic, equilibrium and thermodynamic data of adsorption studies were processed to understand the mechanism of Methylene blue (MB) onto modified Lantana biomass.

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of Methylene blue.

Results and discussion

Characterization of adsorbent :

The IR spectra of Lantana biomass in its raw form and modified have been displayed in Fig. 2. The IR spectrum of Lantana biomass exhibits broad band at 3425 cm^{-1} due to the stretching of OH group. The C-H stretching is responsible for absorption band at 2874 cm^{-1} . The absorption band at 1510 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of an aromatic ring. The peak at 1027 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of Si-O linkage. Upon comparing the IR spectrum of raw form to that of modified form, it could be seen that there was a strong characteristic stretching vibration absorption band of carboxyl group at 1766 cm^{-1} in IR spectrum of acid modified form¹⁶. This confirms the result of esterification by citric acid. In addition to this it

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of raw and modified Lantana.

can be also seen that nearly all the peaks of raw form get slightly shifted from its position after treatment of the adsorbent which also supports modification of the adsorbent.

The SEM micrographs for the study of surface morphology of the raw and modified adsorbent (Figs. 3a and 3b) evidently reveals the presence of enormous rugged and grooved features at adsorbent surface after modification. These rough surface increases the surface area of the adsorbent which further helps in binding of dye molecules.

Fig. 3a. Lantana biomass raw form.

Effect of pH :

It is reported that the change of pH affects the adsorptive process through dissociation of functional groups on the adsorbent and adsorbate¹⁷. pH also controls the degree of ionization and speciation of the species in solution. In the present investigation the removal of Methyl-

Fig. 3b Lantana biomass modified with citric acid.

ene blue dye by modified Lantana biomass was studied at various pH values. A maximum removal (98.1%) of the dye was achieved at pH 8 and gets decreased with the decrease of pH value (Fig. 4). With an increase of pH from 2 to 8, the uptake of cationic dye molecules increased from 46.2% to 98.1% for the adsorbent at 323 K, agitation speed 180 rpm, and concentration 10 mg/L of the dye. Removal of dye molecules at higher pH contributed to the presence of negatively charged hydroxyl ions which influences the adsorbent surface and tends to establish negative charge over the surface which leads to attraction of positively charged dye molecules over the adsorbent surface by electrostatic force of attraction.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on removal of MB (adsorbent dose : 5 g/L; dye concentration : 10 mg/L and Temperature 323 K).

The adsorption depends not only on initial pH but also zero point charge of the adsorbent (pH_{zpc}). The zero

point charge was found to occur at the pH of 5.5. As reported elsewhere¹⁷, the surface of the adsorbent will be negatively charged above pH_{zpc} and positively charged below pH_{zpc} . Since, Methylene blue is the basic dye, maximum adsorption occurred at pH ranging from 2 to 8.

Effect of contact time and initial dye concentration :

The effect of contact time for the removal of MB by the Lantana biomass has been studied at different initial concentrations (10, 25, 50 and 100 mg/L) of dye solution with adsorbent of 5 g/L. From Fig. 5 it can be seen that rapid adsorption of dye takes place within duration of 20 min and thereafter, the adsorption rate decreased gradually and the adsorption reached equilibrium in about 30 min. Further experiments were conducted for 30 min contact time only.

Fig. 5. Effect of initial concentration on uptake (adsorbent dosage : 5 g/L; pH 7 and Temperature 323 K).

Accordingly all batch experiments were conducted with a contact time of 30 min under shaking speed of 180 rpm. A large number of vacant surface sites are available for binding of dye molecules during the initial stage and after a lapse of time, the remaining vacant surface sites are difficult to be occupied due to repulsive forces act between the solute molecules adsorb on the solid and in bulk phases¹⁸. Therefore rapid adsorptions of dye molecules followed by slowing down of adsorption takes place as the adsorbate molecules have to penetrate deeper into the pores of adsorbent materials this leads to encounter greater degree of resistance.

Effect of contact time and temperature :

In the present experiment the rates of removal at three different temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K) have been

observed (Fig. 6). The rate of dye uptake increases noticeably from 89.2% (1.77 mg/g) to 97.5% (1.95 mg/g) with increasing temperature from 303 K to 323 K with 5 g/L dose in 30 min at the attainment of equilibrium from 10 mg/L of dye solution. The increase in adsorption capacity of modified Lantana biomass with increase of temperature indicates an endothermic process. The increase in adsorption capacity with temperature may be attributed to either increase in active sites over surface of adsorbent available for adsorption or decrease in the thickness of the boundary layer surrounding the adsorbent with temperature, so that the mass transfer resistance of dye molecules in the boundary layer decreases¹⁹.

Fig. 6. Effect of temperature on dye removal (adsorbent dosage : 5 g/L; initial concentration : 10 mg/L and pH 7).

Adsorption kinetics for the dye removal :

Pseudo-first order model :

In this study, adsorption kinetics models, i.e. pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order and intraparticle diffusion were used to fit the adsorption kinetic experimental data. The kinetic models in linear form are expressed as follows :

Pseudo-first order model²⁰ :

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - (K_{ad}/2.303).t \quad (1)$$

Pseudo-second order model²¹ :

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + 1/q_e t \quad (2)$$

where K_{ad} and k_2 are the rate constants of pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order (Fig. 7) respectively. The value of k_1 was determined from slope of the linear plots of ' $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t ' for different concentrations. The

values of q_e and k_2 for pseudo-second order kinetic model can be determined by the slope and intercepts of the straight line of the plots ' t/q_t vs t ' respectively (Fig. 7). The values of K_{ad} , k_2 , h , calculated q_e , experimental q_e and correlation coefficients, R^2 for different concentrations ranges

Fig. 7. Pseudo-second order kinetics plot (adsorbent dosage : 5 g/L; initial conc. : 10 g/L; pH 7 and Temperature 323 K).

are given in Table 1. The kinetics models were fitted with the experimental data and their constants were summarized in Table 1. The pseudo-second order gives bet-

Table 1. Calculated kinetic parameters for the sorption of MB onto Lantana biomass

Pseudo-first order :

Temp. (K)	k_1 (L/min)	R^2	$q_{e,cal}/q_{e,exp}$ (mg/g)
303	0.101	0.987	1.08/1.82
313	0.117	0.990	1.12/1.91
323	0.134	0.977	1.22/1.95

Pseudo-second order :

Temp. (K)	k_2 (g/mg/min)	h (mg/g/min)	R^2	$q_{e,cal}/q_{e,exp}$ (mg/g)
303	0.149	0.584	0.998	1.98/1.82
313	0.140	0.618	0.997	2.1/1.91
323	0.158	0.72	0.997	2.16/1.95

Intra-particle diffusion :

Temp. (K)	K_{id} (mg g ⁻¹ min ^{-1/2})	C	R^2
303	0.188	0.839	0.996
313	0.193	0.912	0.997
323	0.196	0.951	0.998

ter correlation coefficient, R^2 0.99, as compared to the pseudo-first order. The values of the q_e estimated using pseudo-second order model were consistent with the experimental data, suggesting the availability of this model for the adsorption process.

Intra-particle diffusion study :

To confirm the possibility of intra-particle diffusion in present system, the kinetic data were analyzed by intra-particle diffusion using well known Weber-Morris intra-particle diffusion model²² :

$$t^{1/2} = k_{id} + C \tag{3}$$

The values of k_{id} and C can be calculated from the slope and intercept respectively from the plot q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ (Fig. 8). In the above expression (eq. 3) the value of the intercept ‘ C ’ is related to the thickness of the boundary layer. In case of higher values of ‘ C ’, intra-particle diffusion will be rate limiting step. Intra-particle diffusion will be the rate limiting step if the regression of q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ is

Fig. 8. Intra-particle diffusion study (adsorbent dosage : 5 g/L; initial conc. : 10 g/L; pH 7 and Temperature 323 K).

linear and passes through the origin²³. In the present study intra-particle diffusion is not the only rate limiting step. The values of k_{id} for different concentrations are given in Table 1. In case of involvement of intra-particle diffusion the plot of uptake (q_t) versus the square root of time will be linear and lines will pass through the origin.

Adsorption isotherm :

The adsorption data obtained from the adsorption iso-

therm experiments were fitted with Langmuir, Freundlich and Harkins-Jura isotherm models. These models can help in explaining the adsorption behavior of the adsorbate (MB) onto the adsorbent.

Langmuir isotherm model :

Langmuir isotherm model assumes that there are uniform energies of adsorption at the surface of adsorbent and after adsorption; there is no migration of adsorbate molecules on the surface plane. Langmuir isotherm can be represented in linearized form²⁴

$$C_e/q_e = 1/Q_{max}b + C_e/Q_{max} \tag{4}$$

where C_e (mg L^{-1}), q_e (mg g^{-1}) are the concentrations of adsorbate and amount of adsorbate adsorbed at equilibrium, respectively. The constant b (L/mg) is the Langmuir equilibrium constant and Q_{max} gives the theoretical monolayer saturation capacity. The values of various parameters are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Various calculated parameters of the adsorption isotherms

Langmuir isotherm :				
Temp. (K)	Q_{max}	b	R_L	R^2
303	20.94	0.101	0.092	0.97
313	24.39	0.115	0.084	0.976
323	27.77	0.142	0.065	0.959
Freundlich isotherm :				
Temp. (K)	K_F	$1/n$	R^2	
303	2.14	0.668	0.998	
313	2.91	0.603	0.993	
323	4.54	0.572	0.968	
Harakins-Jura isotherm :				
Temp. (K)	B_2	A	R^2	
303	106.04	9.23	0.929	
313	63.38	8.24	0.919	
323	33.21	5.37	0.899	

The essential factor of Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in term of a dimensionless constant called separation factor (R_L , also called equilibrium parameter) which is defined by following equation :

$$R_L = 1/1 + b C_0 \tag{5}$$

where C_0 (mg/L) is the initial adsorbate concentration and b is the Langmuir constant. The value of R_L indicates the shape of the isotherm to be either unfavorable ($R_L > 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$) and favorable ($R_L < 1$). In present

study all the values of R_L were found to be less than 1 which indicates that adsorption is favorable. The comparison of maximum monolayer adsorption capacity of the various adsorbents for the MB dye removal was given in Table 3. It shows that modified *Lantana camara* biomass studied in this work has comparable adsorption capacity than that of reported natural adsorbents.

Table 3. Comparison of maximum adsorption capacity (Q^0) of different adsorbents towards MB

Adsorbent	Maximum adsorption capacity Q^0 (mg/g)	Ref.
Mango seed powder	142.85	2
Jute processing waste	22.47	3
Rice husk	40.55	4
Wheat shell	21.50	5
Marine green alga	40.2	6
Yellow passion fruit waste	44.70	7
Guava leaf powder	295	8
Meranti saw dust	120.0	9
Cotton stalks	4.52	10
Cotton waste	8.33	10
Cotton dust	9.75	10
Carrot leaf powder	66.6	11
Carrot stem powder	55.5	11
Milled sugarcane	30.7	12
Strychnos potatorum seeds	78.84	13
<i>Lantana camara</i>	27.77	This study

Freundlich isotherm model :

The Freundlich isotherm is based on both monolayer (chemisorption) and multilayer adsorption (physisorption) with interaction between adsorbed molecules.

The Freundlich isotherm model²⁵ is expressed as :

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e \quad (6)$$

K_f (mg g⁻¹) is the Freundlich constant and n is the Freundlich exponent. The equilibrium data was plotted for $\log q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ enables the constant K_f and exponent $1/n$ to be determined q_e is the amount adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbate, C_e the equilibrium concentration, and $1/n$ and K_f are constants. The constant K_f is related to the degree of adsorption, $1/n$ provides the tentative estimation of the intensity of the adsorption. The values of Freundlich parameters ' K_f ' and ' $1/n$ ' are given in Table 2. Linear plots (Fig. 9) and higher correlation coefficient values confirm the applicability of Freundlich

Fig. 9. Freundlich isotherm plot for removal of MB onto Lantana biomass at different temperatures.

isotherm model to the system. This might be due to the multilayer adsorption of MB on porous structure of the Lantana biomass.

Harkin-Jura isotherm model :

Harkin-Jura isotherm²⁶ assumes the possibility of multilayer adsorption with the existence of heterogeneous pore distribution.

H-J isotherm equation can be expressed as follows :

$$1/q_e^2 = (B_2/A) - (1/A) \log C_e \quad (7)$$

where A and B were the isotherm parameters which were calculated from the slope and intercept of plot $1/q_e^2$ versus $\log C_e$ values are given in Table 2.

Thermodynamics studies :

Thermodynamic parameters such as change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) were determined using the following equations²⁷ :

$$K_c = q_e/C_e \quad (8)$$

where K_c is equilibrium constant, q_e and C_e are the equilibrium concentration of dye ions on adsorbent (mg/g) and in solution (mg/L) respectively. The change in free energy (ΔG) can be calculated from the relation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_c \quad (9)$$

where, T is temperature in Kelvin and R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol K).

Enthalpy change (ΔH) was calculated from the following equation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (10)$$

$$\log K_c = -H^\circ/RT + S^\circ/R \quad (11)$$

ΔH° and ΔS° were obtained from the slope and intercept of Von't Hoff plots of $\log K_c$ versus $1/T$ (Figure not given). The values of the thermodynamic parameters are present in Table 4. Positive value of ΔH° indicates that adsorption process is endothermic in nature. The negative value of ΔG° indicates the feasibility and spontaneity of the adsorption process. The decrease in value of free energy with increase in temperature suggests that the process of removal becomes more spontaneous at increasing temperature. The positive value of ΔS° attributed to the increasing randomness at solid-liquid interface.

Table 4. Calculated thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of MB onto Lantana biomass

Temp. (T) (K)	Standard Gibbs free energy change ΔG_{ads} (kJ/mol)	Standard enthalpy change ΔH_{ads} (kJ/mol)	Standard entropy change ΔS_{ads} (J/mol K)
303	-0.788	19.41	66.34
313	-1.448		
323	-2.108		

Conclusion

Lantana which is considered as an agriculture menace, its biomass can be used as an adsorbent for the removal of MB from aqueous solutions. The modification of adsorbent with citric acid introduced free carboxyl groups which enhanced uptake of cationic molecules. Maximum removal for each concentration ranges has been achieved in 30 min. The pseudo-second order model best described the kinetics of adsorption process. Various iso-

therm models were applied in order to investigate the removal process out of which Freundlich model consider to be the suitable one. Thus from this study it can be conclude that modified Lantana biomass can be a potential adsorbent material for the removal of dye compounds from aqueous solution, in which its adsorption capacity is higher than many others agricultural adsorbents.

Materials and methods :

Adsorbent :

Lantana camara used in the study were collected from the field of the University campus. The collected materials that include stem part only washed several times with tap water and finally with distilled water to remove any adhering dust then dried in sunlight until all the moisture evaporated. The dried material then modified with citric acid by following procedure reported by Vaughan *et al.*²⁸. For this 20 g of Lantana biomass was taken in 500 mL flask and 0.6 M citric acid solution was added (1 : 12 w/v of Lantana/citric acid). Resulting mixture was stirred for 30 min to make the slurry, which was poured on stainless steel tray and was kept at 50 °C for 24 h in an oven followed by increase in temperature up to 120 °C, where thermochemical reaction takes place between Lantana biomass and citric acid. After cooling the resulting material was washed with deionized water until turbidity disappears when 0.1 mole lead nitrate was added dropwise. After filtration solid was dried in oven at 70 °C. Resulting materials, citric acid modified Lantana biomasses were kept in desiccators for use as an adsorbent.

The chemical modification of Lantana biomass (LB-OH) by citric acid may be expressed schematically as :

Adsorbate :

The cationic dye (MB), in commercial purity, was used without further purification. The MB stock solution was prepared by dissolving accurately weighted dye in distilled water to the concentration of 500 mg/L. The experimental solutions were obtained by diluting the dye stock solution in accurate proportions to different initial concentrations.

Characterization of adsorbent :

The adsorbent characterize for the determination of functional groups presenting in Lantana biomass before and after modification with the help of Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (ABB FTLA-2000, Canada).

The study of the surface morphology of the modified adsorbent has been performed by the Scanning Electron Microscope (Fei Quanta 200F, Netherland) at 20 kV accelerated voltage.

Batch mode Experiments :

In the present study batch experiments were conducted in order to achieve the optimum operating conditions for the treatment process. For each experimental run 50 mL of known concentration of dye and adsorbent was taken in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask. The mixture was shaken mechanically at constant speed of 180 rpm using water bath shaker (Mac-Macro Scientific Works Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, India). The samples were withdrawn after pre-determined time, and kept it for 24 h for saturation. Thereafter the adsorbent was separated from the solution by centrifugation using Remi centrifuge machine (Model-R-8CBL). The residual dye concentration was estimated in supernatant spectrophotometrically on double beam spectrophotometer (Model-2203 Systronics, Ahmadabad, India) over a wavelength range of 664 nm.

Adsorption kinetics investigations were carried out by agitating 50 mL of dye solution of known initial dye concentration with 5 g/L of adsorbent at temperature of 303 K at a pH of 7.0 ± 0.1 at a constant shaking speed of 180 rpm at different interval of time. The amount of dye adsorbed onto the adsorbent at equilibrium, q_e (mg/g), can be calculated by using relationship :

$$q_e = (C_0 - C_e) V/W \quad (12)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and equilibrium dye concentration in mg/L respectively, V is the volume of solu-

tion (L) and W is the mass of adsorbent (g). The amount of adsorption at time t , q_t (mg/g) was calculated by :

$$q_t = (C_0 - C_t) V/W \quad (13)$$

where C_0 and C_t in mg/g are the liquid phase concentration of dye at initial and any time t , respectively. V is the volume of solution (L) and W is the mass of dry adsorbent (g).

Similarly for the adsorption isotherm experiments were conducted by contacting 5 g/L of adsorbent with 50 mL of dye solution of various initial concentrations (10 mg/L, 25 mg/L, 50 mg/L and 100 mg/L). The samples were agitated in water bath at constant speed of 180 rpm at varied temperature (303, 313 and 323) K for 30 min which is the equilibrium time. The residual dye concentrations were determined in the same way as mentioned above.

Blank experiments were also conducted by using dye solution without adsorbent to ensure that no dye adsorbed onto the containers and with adsorbent and water only to check that no leaching occurred, which would rather interfere with the measurement of dye concentrations on the spectrophotometer. All adsorption experiments were performed in triplicate and the mean values were use in data analysis.

Evaluation of zero point charge (pH_{zpc}) :

A series of 50 mL of 0.01 M NaCl solution was placed in a closed Erlenmeyer flask. The pH was adjusted to a value between 2 and 12 by adding 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH solution. Then 0.15 g of each sample was added and agitated at 150 rpm for 48 h under atmospheric conditions. The final pH measured using pH meter (Model-335 Systronics) and the results were plotted with pH (Initial pH - Final pH) against final pH. The pH_{zpc} is the point where the curve pH_{final} versus $pH_{initial}$ crosses the line $pH_{initial} = pH_{final}$.

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